

ROSIE

D7.2 Report on the results of piloting the training materials

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1 ROSiE training materials

Work package 7 (WP7) of the ROSiE project is aimed at developing training materials. The main objective of this work package is to develop training materials with and for students, researchers, and citizen scientists for acquiring skills required for responsible Open Science (OS).

The first task (T7.1) in WP7 was the development of a didactic framework including specific learning outcomes and indicators for their achievement, as well as defining topics which should be covered by training materials (deliverable D7.1.).

Figure 1 WP7 tasks and their timing

As a next step, the ROSiE consortium developed the first version of training materials (T7.2) aimed at different groups of trainees - students, early career and experienced researchers

and citizen scientists with different backgrounds. In each field of science (natural sciences, social sciences, humanities, health and life sciences), training materials for a two-day training course were developed. The training materials were complemented by a set of instructions supporting trainers in using the materials, as well as with handouts, printouts, and readings for trainees.

As a supplementary material, a collection of 29 case studies was developed. Case studies were developed in collaboration with WP1 and discussed during a workshop in Tartu in June 2022. After each case, questions for discussion, as well as supplementary readings that may be used by the trainer or assigned as required or optional readings for trainees were included. Part of the case studies were used in the training materials; however, the trainers were encouraged to use the cases also outside the two-day training program to address topics that are not directly addressed in the training materials. Also, the case studies can be used independently from the training materials for any course including ethical issues in the context of open science.

Figure 2 Fields of science covered by training materials

The training materials for each field of science include eight units which together build a full two-days training course. For example, the “Social sciences” training material includes the following eight units:

- Unit 1. Ethical and societal foundations of OS, its purpose
- Unit 2. Protection of research participants' rights in OS

- Unit 3. Ethical aspects of citizen science in the context of OS
- Unit 4. Protection of intellectual property in the context of OS
- Unit 5. The quality of the research outputs and data sets
- Unit 6. Responsible sharing and reuse of open social science data
- Unit 7. Prevention of research malpractice in the context of OS
- Unit 8. Responsible dissemination/publication practices

Each unit includes one or two alternative activities. If there are two activities included in a unit, the trainer can choose the most appropriate activity for the audience. Each activity is supplemented by handouts, printouts, and readings.

Figure 3 Structure of training materials

2 Process of piloting

In September 2022 a call for piloting ROSiE training materials was launched. On the ROSiE webpage and in social media, the ROSiE project invited to apply trainers interested to test the training materials at their institutions. Trainers were suggested to test the whole training material or just parts of it by integrating them into already existing courses or training programs. After piloting, the trainers were asked to evaluate the training materials and give feedback. For feedback collection, WP7 developed an online feedback form.

On September 6, 2022, WP7 organized an introductory online workshop for ROSiE consortium members to inform about the piloting process and to encourage consortium members to share information about the piloting. On October 4, an online workshop for potential participants of piloting was organized for stakeholders outside of the consortium. The recording of this workshop was made available to all participants and those who were not able attend the workshop.

To exchange experience, discuss the results of pilot testing and define necessary amendments in training materials, WP7 organized an onsite workshop in Riga, in March 2023 (Milestone M7.5).

Figure 4 Workshops for piloting training materials

In total, 25 trainers applied for piloting the ROSiE training materials. The deadline for comments from trainers on the draft version of training materials was set for March 15, 2023. By this date, WP7 got 16 filled in feedback forms from 12 trainers (some trainers piloted several packages of the training material and provided separate feedback for each part). Additionally, one trainer preferred providing feedback during an online meeting. The list of trainers who provided feedback is as follows (the trainers agreed to be listed as reviewers):

- 1) **Rosemarie Bernabe**, University of Oslo and University of South-Eastern Norway (Norway)

- 2) **Sandra Bendiscioli**, EMBO - European Molecular Biology Organization
- 3) **Stephanos Cherouvis**, Ecsite - European network of science centers and museums 4) **Ilaria Anna Colussi**, BBMRI-ERIC
- 5) **Keziah Chanyisa Khayadi Dash**, University of Oslo and University of South-Eastern Norway (Norway)
- 6) **Su Nee Goh**, Nanyang Technological University (Singapore)
- 7) **Eva Hnátková**, National Library of Technology (Czech Republic)
- 8) **Margarita Poškutė**, Vilnius University (Lithuania)
- 9) **Vivian Mbanya**, University of Oslo and University of South-Eastern Norway (Norway)
- 10) **Lilian Kwamboka Mocheche**, University of Oslo and University of South-Eastern Norway (Norway)
- 11) **Mari-Liisa Parder**, University of Tartu (Estonia)
- 12) **Vana Stavridi**, National Technical University of Athens (Greece)
- 13) Additionally, the team at the University of Latvia who were the authors of training materials, piloted the materials by including the topics in Master and PhD level courses on research ethics.

3 Piloting results

Information about results of the pilot testing was collected from two sources:

- 1) **feedback forms** filled in by trainers who piloted the training materials; 2) discussions during the **WP7 workshop on piloting results** in March 2023.

The feedback forms showed that the trainers involved in piloting used all packages of training material, as shown in the diagram. The package on health and life sciences was used the most (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 Packages of training materials used for piloting

All trainers strongly agreed that the instructions for trainers were useful, understandable, and supportive (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 Assessment of instructions for trainers

Also, the usefulness and understandability of handouts and printouts was highly rated (see Figure 7).

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Figure 7 Assessment of handouts and printouts

Figure 8 Assessment of helpfulness to achieve the learning outcomes

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Regarding the question on how helpful the particular unit or activity was to achieve the planned learning outcomes; the respondents' views were split between answers »strongly agree« and »agree« (see Figure 8).

Figure 9 Assessment of topics included in the training materials

The views of respondents regarding the comprehensiveness of the topics included in training materials, as well as regarding how well the topics meet the needs of trainees were mostly positive; however, the answers "neither agree nor disagree" show the potential to improve this aspect of the training materials (see Figure 9).

Overall, the trainers expressed readiness to use the training materials in their teaching (see Figure 10).

Figure 10 Readiness to use training materials

Regarding the attractiveness of the training materials (how engaged were the participants?), the answers showed a potential for improvement, since half of responses were »neither agree nor disagree« (see Figure 11).

Figure 11 Engagement with training materials

3.1 Content of training materials

In the feedback forms the trainers provided several comments regarding the content of training materials. For the “Health and life sciences” package, there was a suggestion to amend topics with additional case studies, e.g., pre-registration of studies, open peer review, and reproducibility.

For the set of 'Health and life sciences' training materials, it may be useful to include case studies on topics such as open methods, e.g., pre-registration, open code, open peer review, and reproducible research. NIH provides several case studies and one of them is on research reproducibility.

For Unit 1 of the “Health and life sciences” package, there was a suggestion to provide additional readings:

For Unit 1, maybe you would want to add a couple of articles focused on the health and life sciences, e.g. <https://www.science.org/doi/epdf/10.1126/science.adg8142> or <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6513108>

Suggestion by another trainer for “Health and life sciences” package was to change readings for Unit 3 for this target group.

*This training material is designed for trainees of health and life sciences. Maybe another more medically oriented paper would be better for healthcare trainees? I mean to provide another printout, such as Wignins, A., Wilbanks, J. (2019). The rise of citizen science in health and biomedical research. *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 19(8), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15265161.2019.1619859> from "Further readings" or Fiske, A., Prainsack, B., & Buyx, A. (2019). Meeting the needs of underserved populations: setting the agenda for more inclusive citizen science of medicine. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 45(9), 617-622. <https://jme.bmj.com/content/45/9/617>*

Regarding the »Humanities« package, the overall assessment was positive:

I worked on the humanities case studies. The content is extremely helpful. The cases have been selected carefully and they are presented in accessible language. [...] I find particularly useful the example concerning the Russian-Ukrainian war. We are currently working with a Ukrainian research institution (in the framework of a Horizon Europe project) and would like to make that known, given that we quickly responded to Europe's call to support Ukraine. We want to share our experiences in a way that encourages others to form synergies with Ukrainian organizations. At the same we are in fear of attracting the wrong type of attention and endanger the people who we are working with.

One trainer suggested shortening readings for Unit 1 which is similar for all training packages.

Maybe making trainees read the first three parts of the UNESCO recommendation is a bit too much, maybe requiring only part 2 is sufficient to give them a framework to start a discussion.

Regarding Unit 4, there was a general suggestion to cover not only issues of authorship and contributorship in the context of citizen science, but also provide alternative activity for discussing authorship in the context of OS in general.

I understand that it is important to discuss the question of authorship in the context of citizen science, but I suppose that at present the issue of authorship is more important for medical/healthcare trainees in the context of "traditional" science. As it is mentioned in one proposed reading, it can be because of the marginalization of citizen science. Nevertheless, probably the case on authorship in academic science would be met more favorable.

Another suggestion for Unit 4 in the context of humanities was to improve case studies on collaborative authorship.

I felt that case discussing problems in Collaborative Authorship could be improved. Comparing it to the other case studies which they touch upon particular examples this one is a little bit poorer. Maybe an better example of a co-authorship issue could be more helpful.

For Unit 6 there was a suggestion to add more questions for discussion:

In HLU6A6.1 more questions could be added to stir a discussion, e.g. What is the responsibility of journals/editors and reviewers? Would open peer review have helped in understanding the responsibilities in this case?

One of the trainers suggested to amend indicators for achievement of learning outcomes for case discussions:

Regarding indicators for trainees' achievement (in various units), I have some doubts whether students' ability to discuss (especially "to discuss cases with colleagues") is really the best indicator. Some trainees can discuss without having knowledge, based only on their opinion. Maybe it would be better if they were able to analyze, evaluate critically, provide pro and cons arguments, etc.?

3.2 Teaching methods

In general, case studies were evaluated as a useful method, however one of the trainers emphasized that this approach needs sufficient time for implementation.

The case studies were very useful and met the learning objectives. Also, the group discussions created debates that are useful for understanding the concepts of open science. However, I would suggest sticking to the time frame suggested by the authors of the training material, i.e., 90 minutes per activity. And this is because, in our effort to work with as many modules as possible, we reduced the time of the activities with the result that it is not sufficient to discuss all issues that had arisen.

There were also some comments regarding particular units and activities. For Unit 5, it was suggested to clarify the role of the mind map during the classroom discussion.

I understand that the developers want to avoid monotony, so different teaching methods are suggested. But what role does a mind map play? Is it discussed during

the meeting? Then it would be good if it was described in the procedures. And more time is needed for the meeting.

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For Unit 6 in the »Health and life sciences« package, there was a suggestion to analyze arguments for and contra participation in OS activities.

I'd change the indicator for the trainees' achievement. Non-participation in OS does not always depend on willingness. Objective conditions also exist. I would suggest to analyze the arguments to participate or not to participate in OS.

For Unit 8 one of the trainers expressed doubts regarding the application of the Four Quadrant method.

I have some doubts about 4 Quadrant Method, namely "Contextual Features". I suppose that not all trainees will be aware about legal, financial and institutional policies. They should find this information before the meeting. The other suggestion: to give more time for the task that students can find the information they need.

To increase the variety of methods used for case analysis, Jaana Eigi-Watkin introduced Brown's "moral imagination" method during the workshop.

3.3 Interdisciplinarity

One of the questions discussed during the onsite workshop on piloting results was: *how to foster interdisciplinarity in training materials?* The participants of the workshop provided examples where scientists from natural sciences might need expertise in social sciences in the context of OS.

[For example] we have created the platform and we want to obtain feedback from them [members of public], and we have some issues with regard to GDPR compliance, and how open this interaction can be, how open we can disseminate the results of this kind of interaction. [...] This is a total black box for engineers, and we should take inspiration from what social sciences are doing.

One of the trainers in the comments on her piloting experience commented that she used two different packages to ensure interdisciplinarity.

In order to implement as many activities as possible and examine different cases within one training day, we reduced the time of the activities. In addition, in order to respond to an interdisciplinary audience we implemented activities of two disciplines.

A possibly useful methodological approach suggested during the workshop was regarding situations where there is an interdisciplinary group of trainees involved. In such a case it

might be beneficial to form small groups according to disciplinary lines. The small groups representing particular fields of science might be asked to discuss a case from their point of ¹⁵ view. In a plenary discussion following the group work, the different perspectives are discussed. It might help, first, to see the differences that actually exist and find a consensus.

Another methodological approach suggested was 'pairing the cases'. For example, in situations where there is a group consisting of medical scientists and engineers, it might be useful to give them two cases, one medical case and one engineering case, and ask them to discuss these cases in mixed groups.

It was also suggested by participants of the workshop to involve several trainers with different backgrounds, where possible. One of the participants emphasized that the style of argumentation may be different in different fields of science, and, for example, scientists from social sciences may be better prepared to provide the perspective on social concerns. Involving several trainers with different backgrounds might be useful for achieving a dialog between different fields of science and to avoid monologues.

3.4 Citizen science

Fostering responsible citizen science as a part of OS is an important aim of the training materials, addressing both scientists and citizen scientists. There were two types of comments regarding citizen science – from the perspective of scientists and citizen scientists.

One of the reviewers commented regarding the usability of Unit 3, Activity 3 »Development of an ethically sound citizen science project«. This activity involves home reading before the classroom activity, to introduce the concept of citizen science in the context of social sciences. It is followed by group project onsite where trainees are asked to develop their own citizen social science projects and analyze ethical aspects of these projects.

The development of a project for citizen science is difficult. I did show the participants a video of a citizen science project and ask them questions related to the ethical aspects of citizen science. I will prefer a case discussion over developing a citizen science project.

Another reviewer commented that possibly the number of citizen science related topics should be reduced:

Units 3, 4 and 5 are related to citizen science. It may be useful to have more noncitizen science related case studies.

An important point for the reflection during the workshop was suitability of training materials for training of citizen scientists, and participants discussed the following questions:

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- 1) what are the specific needs of citizen scientists?
- 2) how to tailor training materials for citizen scientists?

Based on the workshop discussion, the conclusion was made that the material for citizen scientists should be different from the currently developed material for students and scientists. The workshop participants noted that citizen scientists usually are highly motivated, but they should be approached differently than students and researchers. For example, citizen scientists are not likely to be expected to read the currently suggested readings, e.g., a rather long scientific article, and discuss it.

One of the suggestions on how to train citizen scientists in responsible OS was to make mixed groups consisting of scientists and citizen scientists who will later work together.

One additional discussion point during the workshop was the question whether for citizen scientists the same cases with high moral intensity as for researchers and students should be included. Some participants argued that for citizen scientists, cases which are closer to everyday situations should be developed and used. Other participants opposed that it is easier to discuss cases with high moral intensity, and for such cases it is easier to make the points like, what are the values of conflict, what are the possible courses of action. It was also mentioned that high moral intensity of cases might lead to greater moral sensitivity.

3.1 Competences of trainers

During the workshop some of the participants noted that for successful training an important aspect is the involvement of skilled trainers knowledgeable both on OS and RE/RI. Another participant mentioned that the ROSiE focus group participants discussed that “there is a lack of qualified trainers because nobody covers all relevant expertise - very deep knowledge about ethics and integrity together with expert knowledge on OS.” As a possible solution an option to include some elements of benefiting from the expertise of trainees during the training was mentioned, especially in case of trainings for scientists.

Another participant of the workshop mentioned that it might be useful to make instructions for trainers more detailed, because not all trainers who will use training materials will have a background in RE/RI. The instructions might also be amended by including links to further

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information on particular training methods or alternative ways of organizing trainings, e.g., additional methods for case analysis.

It was also discussed that in the context of ethics and integrity training, an important aspect in instructions for trainers is how to deal with confidentiality and with situations when the trainees report real cases of misconduct during the training.

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4 Next steps

4.1 Content of training materials

- To consider amending the training topics with responsible pre-registration of studies, open peer review and reproducibility issues;
- To consider including additional readings, as suggested by reviewers;
- To amend questions for discussion, as suggested by reviewers;
- To amend case studies, as suggested by reviewers;
- To review and amend indicators for achievement of learning outcomes according to changes made in training materials.

4.2 Teaching methods

- To involve an expert in education in the process of further development of all forms of training materials (both traditional and online materials);
- To develop online version of training materials and publish it online, according to the plan included in the ROSiE proposal;
- To start development of MOOC as an additional form of training materials, not envisaged in the original ROSiE proposal;
- To improve descriptions of the methods, as suggested by reviewers;
- To include Brown's "moral imagination" method for case analysis in training materials.

4.3 Interdisciplinarity

- To include instructions for trainers on how to organize training when working with interdisciplinary groups of trainees;
- To include suggestions for trainers on how to involve several trainers with different backgrounds, where possible.

4.4 Citizen science

- To improve the usability of training materials for citizen scientists and to develop a separate package of both traditional and online training materials for citizen scientists.

4.5 Competences of trainers

- To include suggestions for benefiting from the field-specific expertise of trainees during the training, especially in case of trainings for scientists;
- To amend instructions for trainers, especially for trainers who do not have a background in research ethics or research integrity, e.g., by including links to further information on training methods;
- To amend instructions for trainers with information on how to deal with situations when the trainees report real cases of misconduct during the training and how to protect confidentiality of training participants.

Appendix 1. Workshop agenda and participants (September 6, 2022)

WP7 online workshop on piloting ROSiE training materials

Agenda

September 6, 2022

10:00-13:00 (CEST time zone)

10:00-10:40	Introduction to training materials (Signe Mežinska)
10:40-10:50	The case collection (Ivars Neiders)
10:50-11:20	Questions and discussion
11:20-11:30	Coffee break
11:30-11:40	Incorporation of training materials in the Knowledge Hub (Panagiotis Kavouras)
11:40-12:00	Dissemination and organization of piloting activities (Signe Mežinska)
12:00-13:00	Questions and discussion

Participants:

Rose Bernabe

Jaana Eigi-Watkin

Lisa Häberlein

Søren Holm

Francois Jost

Panagiotis Kavouras

Teodora Konach

Olivier Le Gall

Signe Mežinska

Ivars Neiders

Eleni Spyarakou

Vana Stavridi

Maria Strecht Almeida

Appendix 2. Workshop agenda (October 4, 2022)

WP7 online workshop on training materials

October 4, 2022

Agenda

10:00-10:30	Introduction to training materials (Signe Mežinska)
10:30-10:40	The case collection (Ivars Neiders)
10:40-11:00	Questions and discussion
11:00-12:00	Case discussion

Participants:

Katarzyna Biernacka

Rose Bernabe

Sandra Bendiscioli

Stephanos Cherouvis

Ilaria Colussi

Irene Kavanagh

Tim Kersjes

Ivars Neiders

Rita Santos

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Anna Seliazniova

Vana Stavridi

Goh Su Nee

Sally Louise Williams

Appendix 3. Workshop agenda (March 23-24, 2023)

WP7 workshop on piloting results

23-24 March, Riga, Latvia
University of Latvia, Jelgavas Str. 3

Agenda

March 23	
12:00-12:30	Welcome coffee
12:30-14:00	Introductions and overview of piloting results (Signe Mežinska & Ivars Neiders)
14:00-15:00	Lunch
15:00-16:30	Responsible dissemination/publication practices, case discussion using “Four Quadrant Method” (Ivars Neiders)
16:30-17:00	Discussion and reflection
Dinner at 19:00	

March 24

9:00-10:30	Brown's "moral imagination" method, introduction and practical exercise (Jaana Eigi-Watkin)
10:30-11:00	Discussion and reflection 21
11:00-11:30	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:30-12:30	Prevention of research malpractices in the context of OS, practical exercise (Signe Mežinska)
12:30-13:30	Discussion and reflection
13:30-14:00	General discussion on the next steps
14:00	<i>Lunch</i>

Participants:

Ana Sofia Carvalho

Jaana Eigi-Watkin Lisa

Häberlein

Francois Jost

Emmi Kaaya

Kristiāna Kampare

Panagiotis Kavouras

Elina Koivisto

Teodora Konach

Tom Lindemann

Vivian Mbanya

Signe Mežinska

Ilze Mileiko

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